

The Ibero-American Indicators of Sport and Physical Activity for Sustainable Development

Country Report of Colombia

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This Country Report is the result of intense collaborative work between Colombia's Ministry of Sport and the international cooperation consortium comprising the Ibero-American Sports Council (CID), UNESCO, the German Agency for International Cooperation (GIZ), the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF), and the Research Centre in Sports Science of the King Juan Carlos University (CIDE).

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Introduction

By mandate of the Ministers and High Authorities of Sport of Ibero-America, in 2022, the Ibero-American Council of Sport (CID), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), and the German Development Cooperation – GIZ, formed a consortium to develop the first common indicators to measure the impact of sport and physical activity on sustainable development in the Ibero-American region. Subsequently, in 2023, the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF) and the Rey Juan Carlos University of Spain joined the consortium.

The Ibero-American sport indicators aim to provide countries with regular, standardized and comparable information on the impact of sport on the various dimensions of sustainable development, as well as the periodic evaluation of policies that allows for the identification of opportunities for improvement and the support of achievements and results. Additionally, the indicators seek to facilitate the measurement of the social return on sport, ultimately encouraging increased investment in sport and physical activity. At the XXIX General Assembly of the CID in Cartagena, Colombia, in May 2023, the unanimous approval was given for the creation of 12 indicators and four key data points to be implemented across the region. Furthermore, it was agreed to conduct a pilot implementation of these indicators in a group of applicant countries.

The objective of the pilot study was to validate the relevance and applicability of the indicators so that they may be scaled up to the entire region, as well as to carry out an initial calculation of those for which data is available according to existing information sources. Based on this, a report would be produced for each country on the status of the indicators, along with a cross-cutting document outlining the results and lessons learned.

A first phase of the pilot was conducted in Chile, Costa Rica and Ecuador between August 2023 and March 2024, and its results were presented at the XXX General Assembly of the CID in Washington, D.C. A second phase of the pilot was implemented in Colombia and Peru between September 2024 and March 2025, and its results are expected to be presented at the XXXI General Assembly of the CID.

This document corresponds to the Colombia Country Report, which analyses the status of the indicators and the scope of information sources, as well as the challenges for their implementation in line with the country's institutional, cultural and socio-economic context. Likewise, it establishes the connection between the indicators and the national policies and programs for sport and physical activity, and includes some lessons learned during the implementation of the pilot.

The Colombia Country Report is complemented by the technical data sheets of the indicators whose values could be calculated during the pilot, as well as by the general manual for the preparation of technical data sheets for those indicators whose values could not be estimated at this stage due to a lack of available data. The technical data sheets provide a detailed description of the main characteristics of each indicator and are intended to facilitate their correct interpretation, implementation and scalability. Likewise, these data sheets are essential for replicating calculations and promoting discussion among experts.

In the same vein, it is also recommended to consult the Report on Results and Lessons Learned from the Second Phase of the Pilot, which presents an overview of the progress made by the participating countries and the outcome of the technical assessment of the indicators by those countries. In addition, it includes a list of lessons learned and recommendations for the general implementation of the indicators across the region.

Finally, the international cooperation consortium comprised of the CID, UNESCO, GIZ, CAF, and the Rey Juan Carlos University would like to express special gratitude to the Internal Working Group on Physical Activity of the Colombian Ministry of Sport, whose technical team was strongly involved and committed to the development of this document.

I. Country Context

Sport and physical activity in each country are closely linked to its social, cultural and economic context, as well as to the visions and priorities set out in its strategic policies and programs for the sector. Therefore, to better understand the status of the indicators and the challenges and opportunities involved in establishing a common set of indicators across the region, it is important to begin with an overview of the national context associated with these indicators.

According to World Bank estimates, Colombia is an upper-middle-income country (World Bank, 2025), although it faces significant economic and social challenges that limit the well-being of a large part of its population. Some of its main socio-economic characteristics include: a high concentration of income in a small segment of the population, reflected in a Gini coefficient of 0.546 in 2023 (DANE, 2024b); and high levels of poverty, as in the same year, monetary poverty stood at 33% and extreme monetary poverty at 11.4% (DANE, 2024a).

Politically and administratively, Colombia is organized into 32 departments and 1,103 municipalities (DANE, n.d.-b), although there are also other special divisions such as provinces, indigenous territorial entities and collective territories. Thus, the country has both national and subnational levels of government (PROCOLOMBIA, 2023). Demographically, for 2025, the total population is estimated at 53,110,609 inhabitants, of whom 76% reside in municipal capitals and 24% in populated centers and dispersed rural areas (“DANE – Population Projections,” n.d.; DANE, n.d.-a).

The interconnection between the increase in life expectancy — reaching 77.4 years by 2024 (“DANE – Births and Deaths,” n.d.) — and the continued decline in birth rates reflects a shift in the country’s demographic dynamics (DANE, 2021). Combined with factors such as delayed motherhood and fatherhood, urbanisation, and greater female participation in the workforce, this has contributed to lower fertility rates. These changes have resulted in an ageing population and pose new challenges for demographic planning and social welfare (Bruni et al., 2024).

On the other hand, Colombia is a country marked by a long-standing armed conflict that has caused prolonged violence for more than 50 years, leading to devastating impacts and harm not only for victims, their families, communities, organisations, and public institutions, but also for Colombian society as a whole (Centro Nacional Memoria Histórica, 2013). Likewise, the country faces a variety of social conflicts of different kinds, revealing problems related to the lack of access to and protection of fundamental rights for certain populations and social groups. Other conflicts arise from community grievances against private or public actors, often stemming from situations where these communities perceive a deterioration or threat to their living conditions (Defensoría del Pueblo, 2023).

The 1991 Political Constitution, in Article 7, recognises and protects the ethnic and cultural diversity of the nation. Accordingly, three major ethnic groups are identified: the Indigenous peoples, the Afro-Colombian communities — including the Raizal population of the Archipelago of San Andrés, Providencia and Santa Catalina — and the Rom or Gypsy people. Depending on their location, these groups possess their own distinct identities, customs and traditions, which create internal diversity and make a significant contribution to the country’s cultural heritage. Nevertheless, they remain minorities that face unmet basic needs and conditions of extreme poverty (Parra Dussán & Rodríguez, 2005; DANE, 2023).

Colombia is a social State under the rule of law, organised as a unitary Republic that is decentralised, with autonomous territorial entities, and democratic, participatory and pluralistic in nature. The President of the Republic serves as Head of State, Head of Government and the highest administrative authority. Likewise, the National Government is composed of the President of the Republic, the ministers, and the directors of administrative departments (“Constitución Política de Colombia,” 1991).¹

This national context reflects the country’s multicultural nature, high levels of poverty and inequality, significant demographic changes, and the presence of violence and social conflicts in various regions. These realities highlight the ongoing need for social policies and a stronger State presence across the territories to improve the living conditions and well-being of individuals and communities.

Within this setting, public policies on sport, recreation and physical activity coexist. These policies not only seek to guarantee people’s right to engage in physical practices but also aim to generate social and economic benefits for individuals and communities—contributing to higher levels of development, social cohesion and health across the country.

Physical activity has been part of the Colombian State’s agenda since the early 20th century. However, the development of institutional leadership at the national level has been marked by the following milestones: the creation of the Colombian Institute for Youth and Sport (Coldeportes) in 1968; its transformation into the Administrative Department of Sport, Recreation, Physical Activity and the Use of Leisure Time in 2011; and, most recently, the establishment of the Ministry of Sport in 2019.

As for the legal framework governing the sector, there are two fundamental regulations that support and give direction to its policies. The first is Article 52 of the Political Constitution of Colombia, which “recognises the right of all individuals to recreation, the practice of sport and the use of leisure time, and defines the role of the State in promoting these activities.” The second is Law 181 of 1995, known as the Sports Law, which establishes provisions for the promotion of sport, recreation, the use of leisure time and physical education, and creates the National Sports System (Congreso de Republica de Colombia, 1995). These laws provide the foundation for the various policies and responsibilities related to sport, recreation and physical activity across public entities at both national and subnational levels, enabling the promotion and development of the sector, as well as the organisation of organised sport through federations, leagues and sports clubs.

Although sports legislation in Colombia has evolved through the enactment of more than 50 decrees and laws regulating different aspects of the sector—such as doping control, Paralympic sport, and tax exemptions, among others—all share the goal of strengthening the National Sports System. This system operates through two main dimensions: the public dimension, which encompasses the actions of public entities at different levels; and the organised sport dimension, which includes the Colombian Olympic Committee, the Paralympic Committee, and the federations, leagues and clubs associated with each sport.

In this sense, sports, recreation, and physical activity policies in Colombia are developed at two interconnected levels: national-level policies led by the Ministry of Sports, and subnational-level policies at the departmental, municipal, and district levels, led by territorial sports bodies or their respective representatives, which respond to and respond to the diverse needs of populations and territories within a framework of autonomy derived from the country’s political and administrative decentralization.

¹ Taken from Articles 1 and 115 of the Colombian Political Constitution.

In general, the sector's policies are organised into mission-oriented areas at the national level, structured around the functions of the Ministry of Sport. The first of these areas is the Promotion and Development of Recreation, Physical Activity, School Sport and Community Social Sport; the second is Sports Positioning and Leadership, responsible for promoting elite and high-performance sport in coordination with the Colombian Olympic Committee, the Colombian Paralympic Committee, national sports federations, and departmental and municipal sports authorities; the third area focuses on Resources and Tools of the National Sports System, which aims to ensure sports and information infrastructure to support programmes, plans and high-performance sports events, as well as recreation, physical activity, and leisure initiatives; and the fourth area is Inspection, Oversight and Control of sports organisations and other entities belonging to the National Sports System (Ministerio de Deporte, 2024b).

To develop sectoral policies, there are two main types of strategic guidance. Firstly, there are long-term technical guidelines, among which the following stand out: “Guiding Framework for the Promotion of Physical Activity and the Reduction of Sedentary Behaviour in Colombia” (Ministerio de Deporte, 2022); “Public Policy Guidelines on Sports Science” (Coldeportes, 2015); and “Public Policy Guidelines for Gender Equality in the Sport, Recreation, Physical Activity and Leisure Sector” (ONU Mujeres & Ministerio de Deporte, 2022). All these guidelines serve as key inputs for the creation and development of various sectoral strategies.

Secondly, there are medium-term policy orientations, which are formulated within the framework of the National Development Plan (NDP)—the document that provides the foundation and strategic direction for public policies designed by the President of the Republic and his Government team (DNP, 2022b). In this case, the “National Development Plan 2022–2026: Colombia, World Power of Life” includes a section titled “The Right to Sport, Recreation and Physical Activity for Cohabitation and Peace,” which is further expanded upon in the “Strategic Sector Plan for Sport, Recreation and Physical Activity 2023–2026” (Ministerio de Deporte, 2023c). This plan establishes the following strategic lines:

- I. Democratising access to sport, recreation and physical activity for the population, with a differential and inclusive approach;
- II. Complementary School Sports Programme;
- III. Athletes and Para-athletes as Ambassadors of Peace in the World;
- IV. More Women in Sport;
- V. Sport, Recreation and Physical Activity as Drivers of the Popular Economy; and
- VI. Strengthening the Management and Leadership of the Sport, Recreation and Physical Activity Sector.

The “National System for the Evaluation of Management and Results (Sinergia)” monitors and evaluates government policies and programmes, with the aim of generating high-quality information for decision-making. In this regard, for the sport, recreation and physical activity sector, Sinergia monitors the targets set out in the National Development Plan (NDP) and conducts strategic evaluations of the main national government policies and programmes (“Sinergia,” n.d.).

Within the sector, an “Evaluation of Operations, Institutional Framework and Results of the Ten-Year Sport Plan (2009–2019)” was carried out, which highlighted some of the following achievements for the sector.

The country has made progress in its efforts to guarantee this right. On one hand, the population that participates in the Ministry of Sport’s programmes recognises the benefits that these practices bring to specific aspects of their lives—such as health and academic performance; their relationships within social and family environments; their interests, as a means of engaging with cultural and environmental topics; and, last but not least, the conditions of violence and safety in the spaces they frequent.

I. The quality of the programmes promoted by the Ministry of Sport receives high ratings from beneficiaries, demonstrating the operational capacity not only of the Ministry itself but also of departmental and municipal sports authorities.

II. Although not entirely dependent on the sport sector—and with further progress still needed—there is an important supply of spaces for the practice of physical activities, identified as one of the Critical Success Factors (CSFs) in this evaluation (DNP, 2022a).

At the same time, several challenges for the sector were identified, including:

I. The need to strengthen and expand promotion strategies and increase the coverage of state subprogrammes, as they currently reach only 7.1% of people who engage in physical and recreational activities.

II. The development of strategies to attract private sector resources and effectively link physical activity with health, education, infrastructure and social inclusion policies, taking advantage of the multiple benefits demonstrated by physical activity (DNP, 2022a).

III. The sector’s limited resources continue to pose a significant challenge to the sustainability of all its strategies.

Regarding data sources for the sport, recreation and physical activity sector in Colombia, several can be highlighted. The first is “Sinergia”, which provides monitoring data on the implementation of National Development Plans and evaluations of public policies. Secondly, there are data on compliance with physical activity recommendations in the country from the *National Survey of Nutritional Situation (ENSIN)*, conducted in 2005, 2010 and 2015 (Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social, n.d.).

Additionally, the “Design of the Sports Satellite Account (CSD)”, developed jointly by the National Administrative Department of Statistics (DANE) and the Ministry of Sport, revealed the existence of statistics related to sport, incorporating several questions on physical activity and sports practices into national surveys (DANE, 2022a). The satellite account project is currently under development and is expected to be completed by the end of 2025.

Another important source is the “Global Observatory for Physical Activity (GoPA)”, which compiles three indicators related to physical activity: research, surveillance and policy. These are presented through Country Cards, with editions published in 2015 and 2020, and a new version scheduled for release in 2025 (Global Observatory for Physical Activity, 2021a).

The Ministry of Sport is developing the 2025 National Survey on Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviors. Likewise, work is underway to create, adopt, and implement the Single Information System

for the National Sports System. In this regard, the previous projects work to create and maintain indicators for the development of sport, recreation, and physical activity in Colombia, as a tool for better decision-making in public policy.

It is important to note that, in response to the challenge of increasing physical activity throughout the life course in Colombia, efforts have been made to strengthen intersectoral and interinstitutional collaboration, where the role of the sports, health, education, culture, transportation, environmental, academic, networking, and organizations that promote physical activity, and the private sector, among others, are fundamental to achieving a more active Colombia.

II. Indicator Creation Process

The creation and implementation of the pilot indicators formally began in 2022, when, during the XXVIII General Assembly of the CID (Consejo Iberoamericano del Deporte), the Ministers and High Authorities of Sport of Ibero-America issued a mandate for their development. After three years, following an extensive participatory analysis process for their design and review, the indicators have been applied in pilot studies across five countries in the region—Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Ecuador and Peru—with encouraging results towards their broader implementation across Ibero-America. Figure 1 presents the timeline of the main political and technical milestones in the development of the indicators.

The process of identifying the indicators began with a review of specialised literature on existing sport indicators and their relationship with sustainable development (SGI-CID, 2019; Commonwealth, 2020a, 2020b, 2019; UNESCO, 2018 and 2017), which served as the basis for a conceptual and normative framework document.

Subsequently, an exploratory online questionnaire was conducted to identify priority themes for indicator measurement in the region, with the participation of 83 experts from 22 countries. Of these, 44% worked in government, 11% in academia, 10% in NGOs, 10% in international organisations, 8% in sports training schools, 4% in sports clubs, and 13% in other sectors.

Following this, the consortium—composed of the CID, UNESCO and GIZ—proposed an initial set of 60 indicators to be examined through a broad participatory analysis process aimed at selecting a priority set of indicators for regional implementation. This process included 18 semi-structured interviews with academics, government officials and representatives from international organisations (October–November 2022), during which participants provided recommendations and identified the most relevant and feasible indicators to implement.

In addition, two virtual focus groups were held in November 2022 with 22 government technical representatives, during which participants ranked the indicators according to their importance for development, conceptual clarity and data availability for calculation. A virtual meeting for preliminary validation of the indicators was also held in November 2022, with the participation of 37 government representatives from 17 countries in the region.

Based on the findings from these exercises and considering technical criteria and regional thematic interests, the consortium selected 13 indicators and 4 key data points for a final assessment and selection workshop, held in Santa Cruz de la Sierra, Bolivia, in March 2023. During this in-person workshop, participants analysed the clarity, relevance, feasibility and cost-effectiveness of the indicators, establishing their importance and level of feasibility for implementation. As a result of this workshop, the consortium decided to remove one indicator due to its conceptual complexity and the technical and budgetary challenges involved in producing the necessary statistical data for its calculation.

Figure 1. Timeline of the Indicators Creation Process

Subsequently, the 12 indicators and four key data points were approved by the region's ministries and senior sports authorities at the XXIX CID General Assembly in Cartagena de Indias, Colombia, in May 2023. They also established a mandate for the pilot in a sample of CID member countries.

Thus, in June 2023, the Consortium issued a call to CID member countries to participate in the pilot based on certain basic technical criteria and institutional commitments from the applicant countries. After analyzing the applications, the countries were notified. The first phase of implementation would involve the participation of Chile, Costa Rica and Ecuador, and the second phase, Colombia and Peru.

The objective of the pilot was to validate the relevance and applicability of the indicators for scaling across the region, as well as to conduct an initial assessment of them where possible based on available information sources. The pilot produced a report for each country on the status of the indicators, as well as a cross-cutting document on the results and lessons learned.

A first phase of the pilot was carried out in Chile, Costa Rica, and Ecuador between August 2023 and March 2024, and its results were presented at the 30th CID General Assembly in Washington, DC. A second phase of the pilot was implemented in Colombia and Peru between September 2024 and March 2025, and its results are also expected to be presented at the 31st CID General Assembly.

III. General Progress Overview

Regarding Colombia's results in implementing the indicators, the country managed to calculate the values for eight of the 12 indicators (66.6%) and the total for the four key data points. A summary of these achievements is shown in Table 1. The first column shows the name of the data point or indicator, the second its value, and the third some important observations that will be addressed in greater detail in the following section:

Table 1. Results of the Implementation of Key Data Points and Indicators in the Pilot

Key Data	Value	Observations
1. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes"
2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Ministry	
3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	Desired value is "Yes"
4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Yes	
Indicators	Value	Observations
1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity disaggregated by function	0.27%	
2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	0.26%	Preliminary Data
3. Percentage of the population from 18 to 64 years old, sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age.	51.3%	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of women from 18 to 64 years old, sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age. Percentage of men from 18 to 64 years old, sufficiently physically active stratified by gender and age. 	42.0%	
	61.1%	
4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	12.1%	
5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	Not Available	Necessary to have a school census or survey
6. Percentage of school students (6-12 years old) sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	31.1%	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of female school students (6-12 years old) sufficiently physically active. Percentage of male school students (6-12 years old) sufficiently physically active. 	26.0%	
	35.8%	
7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	Not Available	
8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	36.4%	
9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population from 18 to 64 years old	30.1%	
10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	2.7%	
11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	Not Available	Necessary to conduct a survey for its calculation
12. Percentage of government programs using sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	Not Available	

It is important to note that some data and indicators have slight variations in their names compared to the generic list of indicators. This is because countries use different age ranges in their survey target populations and different accounting and government management categories. For this reason, some indicators are not strictly comparable across countries, which requires future harmonization efforts in some aspects.

IV. Situation of the Key Data Points and Indicators

This section presents the status of the value of key data points and indicators, regardless of whether it was possible to calculate their value during the pilot. For each data item and indicator, a brief justification or relevance for its calculation is presented, as well as its basic characteristics. Likewise, the country's position regarding the status of the indicators and the policies or strategic actions it is implementing or plans to implement to strengthen compliance are presented.

Details for calculating the indicators, as well as the concepts used, can be found in the country's fact sheets document for indicators with values; and in the general guide for preparing fact sheets for indicators without values. The main information fields contained in the fact sheets are: indicator definition, justification, calculation method, unit of measurement, year, periodicity, geographic coverage, sources of information, and concepts used, among others.

Key Data Point 1. There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age

Key Data Point with Value

To support evidence-based policy and program design for sport and physical activity, it is essential to have representative, reliable, and regular data on sports practice and physical activity, especially through representative national surveys on the topic. Similarly, to visualize specific challenges for different population groups, it is essential to disaggregate information by gender, age group, and territory.

Having a national survey on sports practice and physical activity no more than five years old is the first step toward building basic indicators on sport and development, such as the percentage of the population that is sufficiently physically active and the gaps by gender or age group.

In Colombia, the benchmark survey for generating information on physical activity according to the criteria established by the WHO is the National Survey on Nutritional Situation (ENSIN), which has three versions: 2005, 2010, and 2015 (Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social, n.d.-a). Of the five desirable survey criteria, the ENSIN meets four, namely: it is representative of the adult population and for different population groups (children, adolescents, and adults); it is disaggregated by gender; and its methodology, results, and microdata are publicly accessible. However, because the latest version is from 2015, the criterion that the survey be no older than 5 years is not met. Therefore, the data value is "partially."

Table 2. Basic features of the key data point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
There is a national survey within the past five years on sports practice and physical activity, stratified by gender and age.	Partially	2015	(Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social, n.d.)

Country's Positioning

In Colombia, various surveys, especially those from the health sector, have included physical activity as part of their components. These include the 2017 National School Health Survey (ENSE) and the 2015 National Survey of Health, Well-being, and Aging (SABE). However, the survey that includes a module that provides indicators for compliance with physical activity recommendations is the National Survey of Nutritional Situation (ENSIN), which has three versions: 2005, 2010, and 2015 (Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social, n.d.-a).

However, for the Colombian Ministry of Sport, it is a challenge and a mission to provide indicators for the sector and the country. For this reason, it is developing the National Survey of Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviors in 2025. This survey will provide physical activity indicators for different population groups across different domains with national and regional representation.

Key Data Point 2. Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity

Key Data Point with Value

The governmental status of the national governing body for sport and physical activity determines its capacity to establish regulations, design policies, implement programs, and manage resources. It follows that this is a key factor in establishing the scope of the national governing body for sport and physical activity in the country.

It is considered that the most appropriate governmental status for the national governing body for sport and physical activity should be a ministry or a body with a high degree of autonomy and powers similar to those of a ministry.

The governmental status of the national governing body for sport and physical activity in Colombia is a ministry, specifically the Colombian Ministry of Sport.

Table 3. Basic Features of the Key Data Point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
Governmental rank of the national authority for sports and physical activity	Ministry	2019	Congreso de la República de Colombia (2019)

Country's Positioning

In Colombia, the Ministry of Sport was created in 2019 and reflects institutional developments dating back to 1968, when the Colombian Institute of Youth and Sport (Coldeportes) was established. Having the status of a ministry is very important for positioning and generating public policies for sport and physical activity on the national agenda. It also allows for greater coordination with subnational levels, which also promote and invest public resources in sport, recreation, and physical activity.

Currently, work is underway on a redesign and institutional strengthening of the Ministry of Sport to modernize and update certain processes in response to the country's changing realities.

Key Data Point 3. Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level

Key Data Point with value

“Every education system must give due place and importance to education, physical activity, and sport, with a view to establishing a balance and strengthening the links between physical activity and other components of education. It must also ensure that quality and inclusive physical education classes are included as a compulsory component of primary and secondary education, preferably daily.” (UNESCO, 2015a, p. 3).

Physical education (PE) is essential for students' comprehensive education. Its formal inclusion in the educational system guarantees benefits at the physical, emotional, social, and cognitive levels. According to the WHO, physical activity has positive effects on mental health, reducing stress, anxiety, and symptoms of depression (WHO, 2020). Introducing exercise habits from an early age leads to the development of healthy lifestyles, reducing sedentary behaviors in adulthood (Bailey et al., 2009). Similarly, it has been shown that when students are physically active, their academic performance is much higher, as memory, concentration, and problem-solving skills are enhanced (Trudeau & Shephard, 2010).

Taking this into consideration, there is a clear need for data or indicators that allow us to monitor countries' commitment to promoting physical education in the early years of life.

In Colombia, physical education is a mandatory subject nationwide in primary and secondary education (for children aged approximately 6 to 15). Despite this, the curricula do not clearly establish the number of hours per week for this subject, which is why the data is valued as "partially."

Table 4. Basic Features of the Key Data Point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
Physical education is an independent mandatory subject in primary and secondary education at the national level.	Partially	2019	Congreso de la República de Colombia (1994) Ministerio de Educación Nacional (2019)

Country's Positioning

Physical education is mandatory in the Colombian education system. However, schools also have the authority to define its intensity, making it difficult to establish regulations determining how many hours each student should receive.

Despite this, Colombia is adopting a more comprehensive approach to education, with the Ministry of Sports, through the Complementary School Sports Day program in conjunction with the Ministry of National Education, seeking to benefit students with sports, recreation, and physical activity beyond mandatory physical education.

Key Data Point 4. There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity

Key Data Point with Value

Legal frameworks are especially important for expressing fundamental principles and rights of individuals, as well as for making visible the priorities and scope of objectives, strategies, and programs. Hence the importance of having data on the existence of legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and monitor gender equality and non-discrimination in sport and physical activity. Likewise, it must be ensured that these legal instruments are actually being applied in policies, programs, or actions with concrete results.

In Colombia, legal frameworks exist to promote, enforce, and monitor gender equality and non-discrimination in sport and physical activity, and there is also evidence that they are being applied with concrete positive results.

Table 5. Key Features of the Key Data Point

Key Data Point	Value	Year	Source
There are legal frameworks to promote, enforce, and oversee gender equality and non-discrimination in sports and physical activity.	Yes	2023	Ministerio del Deporte (n.d.) Ministerio del Deporte (2023a)

Country's Positioning

In Colombia, the main law is the 1991 Political Constitution. It establishes that women and men have equal rights and opportunities and that women cannot be discriminated against ("CONSTITUCIÓN POLÍTICA," 1991, Art. 43). Likewise, Law 181 of 1995, or the Sports Law, establishes that "The State shall guarantee the democratic participation of its inhabitants in organizing the practice of sports, recreation, and the use of free time, without discrimination based on race, creed, condition, or sex" (Congreso de la Republica de Colombia, 1995). Likewise, there are Public Policy Guidelines for Gender Equity in the Sports, Recreation, Physical Activity, and Use of Free Time Sectors (ONU Mujeres, & Ministerio del Deporte, 2022). In this sense, the Ministry of Sports has a sufficient legal framework that allows it to work towards better opportunities for women in sports, recreation, and physical activity.

Indicator 1. Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity

Indicator with value

Budget allocation for sports and physical activity is an objective measure of the importance given to the sector in public investment priorities, and at the same time, a concrete benchmark for the scope of policies in terms of available resources.

In Colombia, the percentage of the public budget invested in the national entity for sports and physical activity, specifically the Ministry of Sports, was 0.27% in 2024, equivalent to 1,364,340,146,323 Colombian pesos.

Table 6. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national public budget invested in sports and physical activity	0.27% Equivalent to 1,364,340,146,323 COP*	2024	Congreso de la República de Colombia (2023a) Congreso de la República de Colombia (2023b)

* Programmed for 2024

Country's Positioning

In Colombia, the national government projects the nation's general budget, which is approved annually by Congress through a law and after various debates. In this sense, the budget has two essential components: investment and operating.

Furthermore, given the limited budget, there is always a growing need for greater investment in the sports and physical activity sector in order to increase the coverage of promotion and development programs, sports positioning and leadership programs, infrastructure construction, and other initiatives. Consequently, the Ministry of Sports works year after year to demonstrate the benefits and prioritize investments for the sector within the framework of the national government's management.

Indicator 2. Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP

Indicator with Value

Sport and physical activity have a significant impact on multiple sectors and economic activities, but due to the lack of measurements or data records, their importance is not adequately visualized or identified. Thus, having statistics on the contribution of sport and physical activity to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) would help assess their importance in society, understand their relationship with other sectors or economic activities, and also informs the design of policies and programs.

The ideal source of information for the indicator is a satellite account for sport and physical activity due to its accuracy and the ability to properly disaggregate the main economic sectors or activities related to sport and physical activity. However, having this indicator poses considerable challenges for countries due to the technical complexity of its calculation and the financial requirements for creating its data sources.

Notably, Colombia is a pioneer in the Ibero-American region in generating information on the contribution of sport and physical activity to GDP through a satellite account. By 2020, the contribution of sport and physical activity to the country's GDP was estimated at 0.26%.

Table 7. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Valor	Año	Fuente
Percentage of the contribution of sports and physical activity to the national GDP	0.26%*	2020	DANE (2022a) DANE (2022b)

* Preliminary data considering that the satellite account is under construction

Country's Positioning

Economic relations also reflect social relations. In this regard, sport and physical activity in Colombia play an important role in the production of goods and services in the country. Considering this exercise is complex, the Ministry of Sport, together with the National Department of Statistics (DANE), are developing the Sports Satellite Account, which will allow for the annual measurement of the added value of sports-related economic activities at the national level, within an analytical framework extended by the national accounts system. This statistical operation is expected to be ready by the end of 2025 (Cuenta Satélite del Deporte, 2022). However, for this version of indicators, preliminary data from 2020 were used, which are part of the satellite account's construction.

Indicator 3. Percentage of the population from 18 to 64 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender

Indicator with Value

Regular physical activity is one of the most important mechanisms for the prevention and treatment of non-communicable diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, and several types of cancer. Physical activity is also beneficial for mental health, as it prevents cognitive decline and symptoms of depression and anxiety (WHO, 2020).

Therefore, it is essential to have indicators on the percentages of the population that are sufficiently physically active as a tool for diagnosis and policy design. At the same time, given the different needs of people and the inequalities that exist between them, it is important to be able to disaggregate indicators by age, sex or gender, ethnic origin, or socioeconomic status, among other criteria, in order to make visible the inequalities and challenges of inclusion in sport and physical activity policies.

In Colombia, the percentage of the population aged 18 to 64 who are sufficiently physically active is 51.3%, and the disaggregated percentage for women and men in the same age range is 42.7% and 61.1%, respectively.

Table 8. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the population from 18 to 64 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	51.3%	2015	Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social (n.d.)

Country's Positioning

This is a very important indicator in Colombia. Thanks to data from the 2015 National Nutritional Survey (ENSIN) series (Ministry of Health and Social Protection, n.d.-a), it also extends to adolescent and child populations. This indicator has traditionally been used to illustrate the problem of physical inactivity and sedentary behaviors in Colombia. Furthermore, since 2005, a report has been available in the Global Observatory for Physical Activity (GoPA) (Global Observatory for Physical Activity, 2021b), and the WHO Global Health Observatory also includes this indicator as a risk factor for non-communicable diseases (WHO, n.d.) (Strain et al., 2024).

It is important to note that the Ministry of Sport is developing the 2025 National Survey on Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviors, with which the country will have updated indicators on this subject.

Indicator 4. Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old

Indicator with Value

According to the WHO (2022): “Physical inactivity is one of the main risk factors for mortality from non-communicable diseases. People with insufficient levels of physical activity have a 20% to 30% higher risk of death compared to people who achieve a sufficient level of physical activity.”

Indicators on deaths related to physical inactivity are among the most important for identifying the extent of the problem in countries and raising awareness about the benefits of sport and physical activity for health and longer life expectancy.

One of the most important, reliable, and standardized indicators worldwide on deaths due to physical inactivity is the one generated by the Global Observatory for Physical Activity (GOPA) in its “Physical Activity Almanac.”

According to this source of information, in Colombia the percentage of deaths due to physical inactivity among the population over 18 years of age is 12.1%.

Table 9. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of deaths related to physical inactivity in the population over 18 years old	12.1%	2020	Global Observatory for Physical Activity (2021)

Country's Positioning

This indicator originated in communities of physical activity researchers in several countries and has been reported by the Ministry of Sport since 2005 in the Global Observatory for Physical Activity (GoPA) (Global Observatory for Physical Activity, 2021b). Updated data on this indicator are expected in 2025, given that it is directly related to the data that the 2025 National Survey on Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviors will provide once the survey is completed.

Indicator 5. Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education

Indicator without Value

“Physical education in schools and all other educational institutions is the most effective means of equipping all children and young people with the skills, abilities, attitudes, values, knowledge, and understanding necessary for their lifelong participation in society (UNESCO, 2015b, p. 6).

UNESCO recommends that weekly teaching hours allocated to physical education be 120 to 180 minutes depending on the grade level, where the hours “refer to actual learning time in physical education only and should not take into account time spent changing clothes or traveling to specific facilities, nor time spent on other topics such as health” (UNESCO, 2015b, p. 74). To have a reliable indicator, it is desirable that it be the product of a school census, or failing that, a representative survey of all primary and secondary schools in the country.

Currently, Colombia does not have a data source with the aforementioned characteristics to establish the indicator's value. Additionally, no minimum number of minutes has been established. Table 10. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of schools providing the minimum number of minutes of physical education	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

Although physical education, recreation, and sports are considered a mandatory and fundamental area, there is no correlation with the required number of weekly hours, a fact largely linked to the recognition of the institutional autonomy of each school. Consequently, for the country, it is not appropriate to parameterize the allocation of physical education hours in comparison with proposed standards. It should be noted that the country does not have regulations for a minimum number of minutes of physical education in schools. However, and in line with the responsibilities of the Colombian Ministry of Sports, the Complementary School Sports Day program is currently being developed, which generates opportunities for the practice of sports and physical activity for the school population in coordination with the Ministry of National Education.

It is not currently possible to standardize this indicator given the autonomy of educational institutions in Colombia.

Indicator 6. Percentage of school students from 6 to 12 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender

Indicator with Value

In the educational field, the effectiveness of sports and physical education policies must ultimately be reflected in the proportion of sufficiently active students, especially at the elementary level (typically students between the ages of 6 and 12), as this is where important lifelong habits are formed.

Hence the importance of having an indicator on the percentage of sufficiently physically active elementary school students, disaggregated by gender. Additionally, it is important to disaggregate the indicator between female and male students because female students have historically suffered greater delays compared to their male counterparts in multiple dimensions of development, in this case, sports and physical activity.

The ideal source of information for calculating the indicator is a student census or a representative survey specifically designed for this target population. However, in the absence of such data, other estimation alternatives can be implemented, as is the case in Colombia.

Table 11. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of school students from 6 to 12 years old sufficiently physically active stratified by gender	31.1%	2015	Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social (n.d.) Ministerio de Educación Nacional (n.d.)

Country's Positioning

Este This indicator is key for the country. In this regard, Colombia has the 2017 National School Health Survey, which addresses physical activity among schoolchildren and adolescents aged 13 to 17 who receive physical education in schools. However, the age range in this survey does not cover the 6 to 12 age group, which is the primary school age group for this indicator. For this reason, the 6 to 12 age group from the National Nutritional Situation Survey (ENSIN) is used as an approximate percentage, since 95% of the population in this age group is enrolled in educational establishments.

In Colombia, the enrolment rate for the population aged 6 to 10 in 2015 was 96.56%, and for the population aged 11 to 14, it was 95.43%, compared to the existing population (Ministerio de Educación Nacional, n.d.).

The Colombian Ministry of Sports hopes that the 2025 National Survey on Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviors, currently under development, will allow this indicator to be updated for these population groups. Furthermore, as part of the intersectoral work, future studies are planned for the country's educational institutions.

Indicator 7. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs

Indicator without Value

The budgets of public entities and their objectives reflect the government's political and programmatic priorities. In this sense, they constitute an objective measure for verifying government efforts to close gender gaps in sport and physical activity.

However, to have reliable indicators on the proportion of budgets focused on gender programs, these programs must have explicit and verifiable objectives and actions aimed at closing gender gaps.

Currently, Colombia does not have data sources to estimate the percentage of the national sports entity's budget focused on gender programs.

Table 12. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on gender programs	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

For several years, policies focused on access to physical activities with an inclusive approach have predominated in the development of sports, recreation, and physical activity policies. Therefore, budget allocation is made across different programs or strategies that implement these policies, seeking to include different population groups.

The current 2022-2026 Development Plan has a focus called "More Women in Sports." In this regard, the Colombian Ministry of Sports is working to establish an indicator for this investment, despite the fact that, in general, there is no gender-based budget allocation approach.

Indicator 8. Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity

Indicator with Value

Senior management positions in public and private organizations are where one of the most significant gaps between women and men is observed. Hence the importance of monitoring the gaps and progress toward gender equality in management positions in national sports and physical activity entities. This information will support better policies or affirmative action in this area.

Given the institutional and administrative heterogeneity of the countries in the region, the classifications used to identify management positions in national sports entities are not exactly comparable. However, by respecting the country-specific classifications, it is possible to obtain a fairly reliable overview of the indicator in the region.

In Colombia, the percentage of women in management positions in the national sports entity is 36.4%.

Table 13. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of women in managerial positions within the national sports entity	36.4%	2023	Ministerio del Deporte (2023b)

Country's Positioning

Law 581 of 2000 regulates the adequate and effective participation of women in decision-making levels within the various branches and bodies of public power (Congreso de la Republica de Colombia, 2000). Under this regulatory framework, the Ministry of Sport complies with the 30% participation requirement established by this law. The Colombian Ministry of Sport is committed to promoting women's participation not only within the national government but also in other entities within the National Sports System.

Indicator 9. Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old

Indicator with Value

There are notable differences in the physical activity levels of women and men. Specifically, "data show that in almost all countries, girls and women are less active than boys and men" (WHO, 2020, P2). In fact, it can also be seen in most countries in the region that the gap between women and men increases significantly with age.

One of the most important goals of sustainable development is to eliminate gender gaps or differences in their multiple dimensions. Therefore, it is crucial that governments and the general public have indicators that allow them to monitor their progress toward reducing or eliminating gaps in physical activity between men and women.

In Colombia, the gender gap in the percentage of women and men aged 18 to 64 who are sufficiently physically active is 30.1%.

Table 14. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the gender gap among the sufficiently physically active population over 18 years old	30.1%	2015	Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social (n.d.)

Country's Positioning

The gender gap in compliance with physical activity recommendations in Colombia consistently highlights the challenges the country still faces in ensuring that the legal framework protecting women is effectively implemented based on their rights. In this regard, increasing women's physical activity is a priority for the Colombian Ministry of Sports. In this regard, efforts are being made to improve women's socio-emotional skills and provide alternatives so that an active lifestyle becomes part of women's daily lives, ensuring that most women participate in the country's physical activity programs. However, policies seek to reduce barriers for women, such as lack of time, self-confidence, and self-image, which limit women's participation in physical activity.

Indicator 10. Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities

Indicator with Value

The Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities establishes that people with disabilities can participate equally in recreational, leisure, and sports activities. Countries must adopt measures to encourage and promote the participation of people with disabilities in sports activities, ensure they have the opportunity to organize and develop sports and recreational activities, and guarantee their access to sports facilities (UN, 2008).

To implement the provisions of the Convention, it is necessary to allocate public funds to programs aimed at ensuring that people with disabilities have access to sports and physical activity. Likewise, it is necessary to invest in data and indicators that measure whether this objective is being met.

As with other indicators, given the institutional and administrative heterogeneity of the countries in the region, it is difficult to establish homogeneous budget categories across countries that can be accurately compared, at least in this first phase of the indicators' pilot implementation. However, to provide a first approximation, the indicator value is presented in cases where the countries have verifiable and transparent sources of information.

In Colombia, 2.7% of the national sports entity's budget is focused on programs for people with disabilities.

Table 15. Basic Features of the Indicator

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of the national sport entity's budget focused on programs for people with disabilities	2.7%	2024	Congreso de la República de Colombia (2023a) Congreso de la República de Colombia (2023b) Ministerio del Deporte (2024a)

Country's Positioning

The Ministry of Sports has invested resources to support Paralympic sports. Furthermore, it has sought to include people with disabilities in various programs and strategies that promote sports, recreation, and physical activity.

The Colombian Ministry of Sports hopes to continue developing initiatives to include a greater number of people with disabilities in sports, recreation, and physical activity, understanding that they are subjects of special protection by the State.

Indicator 11. Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population

Indicator without Value

People with disabilities are one of the population groups most disadvantaged in accessing development on an equal footing. Therefore, the way to verify whether policies or programs targeting people with disabilities are effectively achieving results is to observe whether their physical activity and sports gaps are narrowing compared to the rest of the population.

To achieve this, it is necessary to have representative surveys on the physical activity level of the population with disabilities, disaggregating them by age, sex, or gender. This poses a significant challenge for countries because a significant investment of financial and technical resources is required to implement the surveys and subsequently the indicator.

In this context, in Colombia, there are currently no data sources available to establish the percentage gap due to disability in the percentage of the sufficiently physically active population.

Table 16. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Valor	Año	Fuente
Percentage of the disability gap among the sufficiently physically active population	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

De According to administrative records from the Ministry of Health, in 2020, approximately 1.3 million people in Colombia had some form of disability. (Ministerio de Salud y Protección Social, 2020). However, there are no studies in Colombia that allow us to determine compliance with physical activity recommendations in this population group and, consequently, determine the gap with other population groups, given the technical difficulties that still exist in their registration and classification.

In this regard, the Ministry of Sport, with the 2025 National Survey on Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviors, hopes to have reference data for this population that will allow for a more precise study of physical activity in people with disabilities, in line with the current formulation of the Guidelines for the Promotion of Physical Activity for People with Disabilities in Colombia.

Indicator 12. Percentage of government programs in health, sports, and healthy living that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence

Indicator without Value

Sport overcomes geographical, social, and political barriers, connects people, communities, and countries, and thus fosters coexistence and social and political inclusion.

Sport for development and peace is conceived as a social intervention strategy that, through the "use of games, physical activity, and sport," addresses explicit peace and development objectives. This perspective "incorporates themes such as gender equality, fostering peaceful coexistence, promoting tolerance for differences, encouraging inclusive behaviors, preventing conflict, and promoting health and well-being" (GIZ, 2021).

For all these reasons, it is highly important to generate indicators on the relationship between sport and the promotion of peace and social coexistence. However, this represents a challenge for countries, as they must guarantee reliable information to obtain accurate and transparent indicators.

In Colombia, there are currently no sources of information available to establish the percentage of government programs that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence.

Table 17. *Basic Features of the Indicator*

Indicator	Value	Year	Source
Percentage of government programs in health, sports, and healthy living that use sport as an instrument for peace and coexistence	-	-	-

Country's Positioning

Sports and physical activity have been included in national agendas as a means of improving public health. However, this indicator is complex, considering that sports and physical activity are not its primary purpose, making it difficult to identify. Furthermore, identifying the entire range of national government programs is an even greater challenge. In this sense, it is important to rethink this indicator due to the technical complexity of quantifying the state's public action instruments.

V. Findings and Lessons Learned

From the outset, it is important to highlight that the pilot has been a very valuable exercise, allowing for information mapping, identifying challenges, identifying opportunities, and preparing Colombian teams for the general implementation of the indicators in the region in the future.

Based on the pilot implementation of the indicators, this section presents some of the most relevant findings and lessons learned documented during the process. Although the analysis focuses on Colombia, in some cases it is conducted from a more transversal perspective for the region with a view to the future global implementation of the indicators.

Given the institutional and administrative heterogeneity of the countries in the region, it is difficult to establish uniform budget concepts or categories across countries that can be accurately compared. However, the pilot has identified areas of opportunity for this conceptual unification to improve the comparability of the indicators for their general implementation throughout the region.

- Similarly, the target populations of national surveys across countries differ, meaning that unless the age ranges used in the surveys are standardized, statistical standardization exercises will be necessary to obtain strictly comparable indicators.
- From Colombia's perspective, proposals have been suggested to rethink some indicators due to data restrictions or the emphasis of its own policies. These proposals will be considered for the final implementation of the indicators.
- Generating the indicators and their data sources requires multidisciplinary and intersectoral work teams. This, in addition to facilitating the calculation and monitoring of the indicators, also increases the national sports entity's capacity to generate data and indicators to support policies and document results.
- Government policy measurement and monitoring capacities can be substantially improved through partnerships with academia or specialized research centers. In addition to their benefits for knowledge generation, such partnerships ensure a certain continuity in the generation of information and the monitoring of indicators.
- Having reliable, regular, and relevant information and indicators requires investment from governments and society as a whole. Specifically, calculating some indicators requires allocating budgetary resources for the creation of new representative surveys, censuses, or administrative records, as well as for developing data collection, monitoring, and evaluation capacities.

VI. Recommendations and Next Steps

To implement all Ibero-American indicators and continue strengthening the country's measurement and data generation capabilities to design policies based on empirical evidence, the following recommendations are proposed:

- Establish a work plan to produce the indicators that could not be calculated during the pilot phase. The plan should include specific steps to identify and develop primary data sources.
- Propose alternative indicators to those for which significant concerns were raised regarding their relevance or applicability to the Colombian context, with the aim of discussing these alternatives in regional forums with other countries.
- Promote mechanisms for international cooperation to share experiences, knowledge and training, and to harmonise, as far as possible, basic concepts related to sport, physical activity and development, as well as measurement methods and public budgetary classifications.
- Establish an interdisciplinary and intersectoral working group (covering sport, health, education, economy and national statistics) to map information sources and indicators related to sport, physical activity and their impact on development, and to propose policies and technical criteria for the generation of statistical information in this field.
- Design a strategy for the monitoring and evaluation of the indicators, which, in addition to implementing the baseline for all indicators, should include an initial follow-up report to track their evolution. The strategy should also set preliminary targets for the indicators.
- Establish a partnership with a local university to jointly develop data sources for indicators, create methodologies, and design mechanisms for dissemination and learning.
- Seek partnerships with financial institutions or international investment funds focused on highlighting inclusion gaps in access to sport and physical activity among women, people with disabilities, Indigenous populations and people living in poverty, through reliable indicators and statistical information.

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